

**D5.3 Provisional report on the
identified research needs of
international stakeholders for
the integration into the
strategic research agenda**

**WP5 Science to policy
translation to stakeholders**

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Contributing partners: BfR, PMT members

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Deliverable	D5.3 Provisional report on the identified research needs of international stakeholders for the integration into the strategic research agenda
WP and Task	WP5; Task 5.2
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Due month of the deliverable	M4
Actual submission month	M5
Type <i>R: Document, report</i> <i>DEC: Websites, patent filing, videos, etc.</i> <i>OTHER</i>	R
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public</i> <i>CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU

Contents

1.	Summary	4
2.	Introduction	4
3.	Sources	5
4.	Descriptions	5
5.	Input from stakeholders	5
6.	Steps taken within EJP	6
7.	Conclusions and next steps	7
8.	List of abbreviations	8

1. Summary

This is a provisional report on the identified research and integrative needs of international stakeholders, which has been provided to WP2 for consideration for inclusion in the Strategic Research Agenda of the One Health EJP. The majority of the first identified needs are research needs.

2. Introduction

Following a One Health approach, the EJP aims to create a sustainable European One Health framework by integration and alignment of medical, veterinary, and food institutes **through joint programming of research agendas matching the needs of European and national policy makers and stakeholders.**

One of the specific objectives of One Health EJP is to exchange and communicate with national and international stakeholders, and in particular the European Centre for Disease Control and Prevention (ECDC) and the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA). Stakeholder liaison actions include developing and maintaining contact with ECDC and EFSA to ensure that the overall objectives of the One Health EJP consortium are in accordance with the overarching policies of the respective agencies in relation to foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance, and emerging threats.

Work package 5 (WP5) of One Health EJP is entitled ‘Science to policy translation to stakeholders’ and it is active during the whole length of One Health EJP (2018–2022, 60 months). The Lead Beneficiary is Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) and the Deputy Lead Beneficiary is Statens Serum Institut (SSI). Identification of the research and integrative needs of the stakeholders (D5.2) includes regular scanning of available documents and transparent dialogue with the stakeholders, with focus on the Key EU stakeholders ECDC and EFSA (D5.1). The main aim is to identify the research needs that are knowledge gaps that, when filled/bridged, could have the highest value for informing decision-making and risk management in EU. A further aim is to avoid overlapping work on topics that are already being addressed in other activities. The stakeholders are actively involved as informants and engaged at the most relevant stages during the One Health EJP; the dialogue is maintained active throughout the duration of One Health EJP. The activities of WP5

ensure that the identified research and integrative needs will be efficiently absorbed by the One Health EJP.

Here, we report on the identified research and integrative needs of international stakeholders, which were provided for consideration for inclusion in the Strategic Research Agenda (WP2) of the One Health EJP.

3. Sources

The Stakeholders Committee members of the two Key EU stakeholders ECDC and EFSA were invited to present their expectations to the One Health EJP at the kick-off meeting (KOM). In addition, European Commission Representatives expressed their expectations towards the new consortium at the KOM. Research and integrative needs were extracted from these presentations and included in the matrix of identified research and integrative needs of international stakeholders (as described in D5.2). Most of the needs listed in the matrix are research needs.

At first, the research and integrative needs and gaps in knowledge and preparedness were added to the matrix, as they were presented at KOM (e.g. directly the same wording as on the Powerpoint slides). The original documents (e.g. scientific opinions) served as the main source of details for the more detailed descriptions.

4. Descriptions

The detailed descriptions of research needs aimed to include all relevant details that were available. The descriptions were compiled based on the original documents on the topic when available. For several of the needs, details were unavailable in the documents. Stakeholders were consulted on the draft descriptions.

5. Input from stakeholders

The dialogue with stakeholders took place mainly by emails (Communication procedure, D5.1). This was due to the fact that the exchange platform, planned for the interaction with stakeholders, was not yet available during the process described in this report. A technical platform for interaction

with the stakeholders to identify research and integrative needs and for other requests for scientific support will be established on the website of One Health EJP.

The identified research and integrative needs and gaps in knowledge and preparedness were discussed with the stakeholders ECDC and EFSA (D5.1, D5.2).

The stakeholders were asked:

- a. Comments in general; Do the stakeholders agree that these are priority topics to take forward?
- b. Comments on how relevant a One Health approach is for these needs
- c. Are there any additional needs we should include on the priority list?

Furthermore, the stakeholders were asked to provide input to and to validate the more detailed descriptions, to ensure that their needs are covered in an appropriate way and at an appropriate level of detail.

The contact persons from ECDC added one integrative need on the list. The contact persons from EFSA confirmed that the list reflects the earlier input from EFSA well, and added three additional needs on the list.

The stakeholders were explicitly asked to evaluate whether a One Health approach is essential for the identified research and integrative needs and gaps in knowledge and preparedness. This was done using a scale from 0 – 5 (0 = not essential at all, 5 = highly essential) and marked in the matrix. This step aimed to encourage considering One Health thinking and approach. The results can inform the actions of WP2 and WP7.

Twelve of the listed needs were scored 5 by the contacts from EFSA, and eight needs by the contacts from ECDC; four needs were scored 5 by both.

6. Steps taken within EJP

The list of identified research and integrative needs and gaps in knowledge and preparedness was consolidated by WP5 using exclusion steps, evaluation of overlap, and formulation of the research or integrative needs in sufficient and relevant detail.

PMT was asked to evaluate whether the identified research and integrative needs and gaps in knowledge and preparedness are within the scope of One Health EJP. WP2 was asked to evaluate whether the identified research and integrative needs and gaps in knowledge and preparedness are already being addressed e.g. in the Joint Research projects or Joint Integrative projects, or in other activities known to the One Health EJP consortium. If a need or a gap is already being addressed, there is likely no longer a need at the same level. Needs excluded and needs identified as topics that are already being addressed in other activities were excluded from the list and moved to a separate sheet in the matrix file.

For the final inclusion, the scores given and the representation of needs of the different stakeholders were considered. Needs that were given only low scores (0 or 1) were excluded and moved to a separate sheet in the matrix file. Finally, all needs ranked 4 or 5 by at least one stakeholder (ECDC or EFSA) were kept, as well as a need from the European Commission, scored 3 by EFSA, to ensure the stakeholders are all represented on the list.

The resulting consolidated list of identified research and integrative needs will be taken into account in the procedure for updating priority topics (WP2; D2.6), and for the updating of the Strategic Research Agenda (WP2; D2.7), which will be the basis for the second call for Joint Research projects (WP3) and Joint Integrative projects (WP4).

All consolidated lists of the identified research and integrative needs will be used to give input to work in the consortium as well as further dialogue with the stakeholders. The lists will be made available for the consortium as well as on the platform where dialogue with the stakeholders (D5.1) takes place, on the website of One Health EJP, as soon as the platform is in use.

7. Conclusions and next steps

The procedure to identify research and integrative needs of international stakeholders works well. The feedback from the stakeholders has been positive and their input has been useful. The majority of the first identified needs are research needs. Several were given a high score for relevance of a One Health approach by ECDC, EFSA, or both.

The provisional first consolidated list of identified research and integrative needs of international stakeholders was provided for consideration for inclusion in the Strategic Research Agenda of the One Health EJP (WP2). WP2 was provided with a list with needs by stakeholder and with a list where the needs were placed in the WP2-matrix (domains, themes). These lists, together with the full matrix file where the exclusion steps are shown, will be made available for the consortium as well as on the platform where dialogue with the stakeholders (D5.1) takes place, on the website of One Health EJP, as soon as the platform is in use. The files are also available upon request from the WP5.

8. List of abbreviations

BfR	Federal Institute for Risk Assessment
D	Deliverable (e.g. D5.1)
ECDC	European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EJP	European Joint Programme
EU	European Union
KOM	Kick-off Meeting
M4	Month 4, second month of One Health EJP: April 2018
PMT	Project Management Team
SSI	Statens Serum Institut
WP	Work Package
WHO	World Health Organization